

D6.4 Current and future bunkering infrastructure of green and blue ammonia

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Executive Summary

Based on our assessments, ammonia bunkering will first be introduced in special cases and well-suited green corridors, before the market possibly matures at a significant size. One such case is ammonia carriers where clean ammonia is available and where less training on safety issues is required; seven such ships are on order. Another case is the ship delivering fertilizer from a green ammonia plant in Norway to fixed ports in Germany. Other ships on fixed routes are also possible.

Considering the likely supply of green ammonia in Australia and the limited number of parties involved, a promising green corridor is the transport of iron ore from three Pilbara ports in Australia to East Asia. A large amount of about 800 Mt iron ore is exported each year with at least 4 000 ship voyages. It should be possible to operate bulk ships on ammonia on this corridor and the calculated tank size is about 4 500 m³. Then the vast majority of these voyages would be fully on ammonia with bunkering only in Pilbara. Bunkering in the other end (China, Taiwan, South Korea, Japan) will reduce the required tank size. In fact, bulk ships have a large fraction of the ammonia-fuelled ships that currently are on order, with up to 13 of the 25 ships to be ready within 2027. About 455 ships would be required for this green corridor, and if all these bulk ships would be used for iron ore on this trade, then about 3% of the iron ore transport from Australia would be green in 2027. A possible development of the ammonia-fuelled ships in place towards 2050 and their total ammonia fuel consumption are shown with S-curves in this work. Bunkering in Singapore is unlikely for this trade, but bunkering in the import ports in East Asia would make ammonia-fuelled bulk vessels more feasible.

Another possible green corridor is the container trade from East Asia to Europe. It is possible to use ammonia if bunkering of ammonia is available in China/South Korea, Singapore, Egypt and Rotterdam. Tank size should then be about 6 500 m³ to cover the vast majority of the voyages. It would be beneficial for the tank size to have bunkering by Sri Lanka and the tank size could be even more reduced with bunkering both in Oman and Gibraltar, cf. map in within the report. Operations to Japan does not increase the tank size as long as the ships can be bunkered in Japan.

The overall ammonia consumption will be significant for these two green corridors with close to 10 MTPA for the iron-ore corridor and more than 10 MTPA for the container trade. For these two trades, the announced clean ammonia projects in Australia could cover the ammonia demand in Australia, East Asia and Singapore. Further west on the container trade, ammonia fuel demand could be sufficiently covered from the announced projects in the Middle East and by Gibraltar.

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1 Introduction

Ammonia has attracted wide interest as a source of zero-emission fuel for shipping [1]. Ammonia does not contain carbon and can be CO₂ emission-free under the right circumstances. Almost all ammonia in use today is made from hydrocarbons, and as such has no carbon abatement advantage. Hence new production capacity for green or blue ammonia needs to be added. We use the term 'clean ammonia' for both green and blue ammonia.

In a previous report [2], a foresight study was conducted to assess the supply and demand of green and/or blue ammonia in the years 2030, 2040, and 2050. In the present report, we consider how the ammonia available for shipping should be distributed to the ships in the beginning of a possible transition to the use of significant amounts of ammonia for ship propulsion.

Before 2021, green ammonia production was exceedingly small, with about 20 kt ammonia produced per year in Peru and with no known production of blue ammonia (i.e. without enhanced oil recovery with captured CO₂). By mid-2023 [3], there are 161 announced clean ammonia projects with a total production capacity of 244 MTPA (million tonnes per year) and it is expected that significant numbers will be announced in the coming years.

They are distributed globally but with a large share of green ammonia projects in Australia and the majority of blue ammonia projects in the USA. Most are in very early stages of development with inherently large uncertainty over their implementation. Access to resources, such as natural gas and renewable electricity potential, as well as the consumption of these resources in the local market, is important factors for production of clean ammonia. For green ammonia, several regions globally have large potential for wind and/or solar power, where local demand for renewable electricity is limited and this untapped potential can be exploited for the export of green ammonia. Green ammonia is in principle scalable, since it only requires renewable electricity, water (including sea water), and air.

Today's ammonia market is dominated by the fertilizer market (80% of the ammonia demand), but clean ammonia aims at new applications such as shipping fuel, power plants, and as a hydrogen carrier. Most of the producers aim to sell ammonia to multiple sectors, with only 26% production capacity committing to a single end use. Many possible off takers will contribute to drive up clean ammonia production.

Likelihoods of implementation were evaluated in the previous report, and about 43 MTPA was estimated to be available in the balanced scenario in 2030. Clean ammonia dedicated to shipping may be in the range of 4–7 MTPA, and including announcements of several end uses the clean ammonia available for shipping is in range 4 to 32 MTPA, cf. Figure 1. For comparison, the modelled demand for ammonia as a maritime fuel in 2030 is estimated to be 2.3 MTPA, increasing rapidly to 62 MTPA in 2040 and 245 MTPA in 2050, cf. Figure 2. The maritime sector will use only green and blue ammonia.

Figure 1: Evolution of availability of clean ammonia for shipping fuel (purple). From Ref. [3].

Figure 2: Modelled ammonia demand in shipping compared to the supply of clean ammonia from announced projects. From Ref. [3].

The total amount of green and blue ammonia available in the balanced scenario is estimated to be more than an order of magnitude higher than the anticipated demand from the maritime sector in 2030. If the announced ammonia production goes where initially stated, there will be sufficient availability for the maritime sector; comparing the supply of green ammonia dedicated to shipping in 2030 with the modelled demand for 2030. Maritime internal combustion engines might be available from about 2025 and hence ammonia demand in the sector becomes possible. The ammonia producers appear to be hedging, and the main approach is a mixture of off takers. The risks are clearly reduced when, instead of only maritime fuel, an investor has three to four distinct end uses in an open market. However, the demand growth after 2030 is steep and accelerating and the supply-demand balance may change rapidly in the 2030s.

2 Current bunkering of marine fuels

Most refuelling operations for deep-sea shipping take place at the major refuelling hubs, which are located strategically along the major international trade lanes. In 2012, the fuel consumption for ships above 5 000 GT in international trade was reported to 212 MTPA [4]. Most of this are oil based, whereas 6% of the fuel consumption is LNG and 0.11% other fuels. However, the majority of LNG consumed is from boil-off in LNG carriers [4].

Vessels typically have tank capacities that allow for several voyages, and hence the ships aim at bunker in locations with low prices. Ships in regular trades, such as container lines, can plan for optimal bunkering location in contrast to tramp shipping that has to ensure sufficient bunker to reach bunkering locations.

Statistics on fuel sold in 2020 show that close to half of all fuel volumes are bunkered at the only 10 major bunkering hubs, cf. Figure 3 [4]. Port of Singapore is by far the largest bunkering hub, accounting for about 23% of total bunker volumes.

Figure 3: Fuel sold in the 10 major bunkering ports in 2020 compared to the total bunkers sold in 2019. From Ref. [4].

Figure 4: Map of 10 major bunkering hubs delivering half of the bunkered fuel.

The Port of Singapore is the largest and most important bunkering port in the world. Its location makes it a natural connection point between East and West trade. Singapore is linked to 600 ports in 123 countries [5]. It is one of the world's busiest ports in terms of total shipping tonnage, total cargo tonnage handled and as a transshipment port, with over 130 000 calls every year. The port of Singapore has 210 bunker barges registered as of 2021 [6]. As the largest bunkering port in the world, Singapore has announced its aim to provide a range of alternative fuels in the future [7].

The Port of Rotterdam is the largest bunkering port in Europe and one of the top bunkering ports in the world. It is a global trade centre for seagoing vessels and inland waterway vessels. The total length of Rotterdam's quays is about 80 km, and data from 2021 showed about 28 000 seagoing vessels and about 90 000 inland waterway vessels visiting the port [8]. Port of Rotterdam stated that it uses 180 different bunker vessels for supplying visiting vessels [9].

Bunkering availability of alternative fuels in key ports along main maritime traffic routes will be crucial to supply candidate fuels to ships. The global fuel and gas oil bunkering infrastructure is in place, a global LNG infrastructure is developing, and bunkering infrastructure for other alternative fuels is almost non-existent.

3 Ammonia initiatives

3.1 Engine developments

A number of marine engine manufacturers are developing engines that can use ammonia as a fuel. This is relevant both for new engines and for retrofit for a range of engines already in use.

MAN B&W will deliver its first ammonia engine to a ship in Japan in 2024 [10]. After trials on this ship, MAN will offer 2-stroke engines to its client in 2027. Between 3 000 and 5000 ships with MAN engines can be modified into burning alternative fuels [10].

Wärtsilä is developing retrofit solutions to 2-stroke engines as part of the Ammonia2-4 project supported by EU, in addition to newbuild 4-stroke engines. The Ammonia2-4 project is running from 2022 to 2026 and as part of the project there will be a demonstration of running a 2-stroke ammonia-powered engine in a container ship. Wärtsilä released 15 November 2023 its 25-bore engine on ammonia fuel [11].

WinGD offers several large engines [12] in the X-DF-A series. X52DF-A, X72DF-A and X62DF-A have been ordered and first expected delivery dates are 2025Q2 and 2025Q3, respectively [13], whereas X62DF-A and X82DF-A are under development. The engines are NO_x Tier II-compliant without exhaust aftertreatment systems.

Other engine manufacturers are also mentioned in the next section.

3.2 Proposed ammonia ships

On 15 March 2024, Maritime Port Authority in Singapore reported that Fortescue Green Pioneer, an offshore supply vessel, successfully completed its ammonia fuel trial, after having converted two of its four engines to run on ammonia in 2022-2023 [14]. It received class notation “Gas-fuelled ammonia” by DNV. The test was carried out with 3 tonnes of ammonia. The ship has pressurized tanks of 40 m³, which is sufficient for two weeks voyage [15].

Figure 5: Fortescue Green Pioneer with class notation “Gas-fuelled ammonia” by DNV

As of June 2024, there are up to 25 commercial ammonia-powered ships on order [16]. In 2024, two ships will be delivered. Both are Asian tugs, and one of them is a retrofit [17]. In addition, Eidesvik Offshore’s Viking Energy has planned to install a 2 MW solid oxide fuel cell in 2024 that will be run on ammonia [18].

In 2025, the first of up to ten ammonia-ready capesize bulk carriers are planned to be delivered, and the series will be built in 2025 and 2026 [19]. The ships are built for CMB’s sister company Bocimar and to be built at CSSC Qingdao Beihai Shipbuilding. The 210 000 DWT bulkers will be equipped with 3 000 m³ ammonia fuel storage tanks and WinGD ammonia dual-fuel X72DF engines [20].

MAN will deliver its 7S60ME engine in 2025 to a bulk carrier owned by K Line, NS United and Itochu JV, and which will be built at Nihon Shipyard in Japan [21] [22].

For 2026, seven more ships are ordered, six of which are LPG/ammonia gas carriers and the last is a container ship. The container ship Yara Eyde is a 1 400 TEU ship, that will be used between Porsgrunn and Oslo in Norway and Hamburg and Bremerhaven in Germany [23]. Yara participates as cargo owner and Yara Clean Ammonia is part of the joint venture that aims to be the first line operator focusing only on ammonia-powered ships [24]. Yara Eyde will be DNV classed and an Azane bunkering barge will be used to bunker ammonia in Brevik in Norway [23]. The ship will be equipped with a WinGD engine.

Belgian Exmar LPG have two LPG/ammonia carriers (46 000 m³) under construction in South-Korea [25] with X-DF-A engines from WinGD and will be delivered in 2026. The fuel supply system will be delivered from Wärtsilä.

NYK has a 40 000 m³ ammonia carrier on order for delivery in 2026, with a main engine from Japan Engine Cooperation and an auxiliary engine from IHI Power system [26]. Both will be dual fuel engines on ammonia.

Tianjin Southwest Maritime have also ordered for delivery in 2026 two LPG/ammonia carriers (25 000 m³) to be fuelled on ammonia [27]. This has subsequently been followed by two new orders for 41 000 m³ LPG/ammonia carrier for 2026 and 2027 [28].

In 2027 Berge Bulk have ordered two bulk ships at CSSC Qingdao Beihai Shipbuilding [29]. In 2027, two crude oil tankers with ammonia propulsion have furthermore been ordered by AET from Dalian Shipbuilding [30].

In addition to the ships mentioned above, several ships are in the process of being realized. Høegh Autoliners have 12 PCTC in the Aurora class in order in China. The eight first ships will be run on LNG, but the ship nine and ten will have MAN ammonia engines [31]. Høegh Autoliners have received a total funding for the two ships of 146 MNOK (about 12.7 MEuro) from Enova. Enova may cover up to 40% of the additional costs, but has been reported to cover less than that for these ships [31]. The ships will sail under Norwegian flag. Høegh Autoliners are also cooperating on bunkering on the US Gulf coast and Singapore [32] and is cooperating with Yara Clean Ammonia [33] and North Ammonia [34] on ammonia supply.

Enova has also granted 180 MNOK (about 15.7 MEuro) funding for Amon Gas (a venture from Amon Maritime) to build two medium-sized LPG/ammonia carriers where both the main engine and auxiliary engine will be ammonia-fuelled [35] [36]. The goal is operation by 2028.

Equinor also had a tender out for 26 April 2024 for supply vessels with dual fuel ammonia engines. Ship owners have according to Equinor shown interest for this [37]. It has not been specified the number of ships and when they will start operating. Furthermore, Equinor and AkerBP are both involved in a pilot for Grønt Skipsfartsprogram (GSP) for a feasibility study for bunkering of ammonia in the Stavanger area in Norway [38]. The pilot is led by Yara.

The Australia mining giant Fortescue Metal Group plan to convert its fleet of eight very large ore carriers to run on ammonia from 2027 [39].

3.3 Current ammonia bunkering ports

As of March 2024, there is no established bunkering infrastructure as there are no commercial ships running on ammonia and expected engine deliverables in 2025 to 2026.

The new fuel ammonia is incompatible with the current bunkering infrastructure of conventional fuels, due to its unique characteristics. In terms of boiling point and vapour pressure, it is similar to LPG (propane). It can be stored either as compressed ammonia at moderate pressure or refrigerated ammonia (at about -33°C). Ammonia is corrosive, which affects the selection of materials and its toxic properties adds complexity to the infrastructure development.

Ammonia is today a global commodity and about 18 to 20 MTPA of ammonia are transported annually. A number of LPG carrier can take ammonia as a cargo and typically 40 carry ammonia on a continuous basis [1]. There are about 215 existing ammonia terminals [16], which may form a basis for a distribution network for the use of ammonia as fuel for shipping.

Since ammonia has lower energy density than oil-based fuel and with the current shape and location of the tanks in the ship, this will, at least in the beginning, lead to reduced range of the vessel. This may imply a shift away from refuelled being dominated by a small number of major bunkering hubs in the future.

Several ports have plans for bunkering at various stages. Port of **Rotterdam** expects to experience its first ammonia bunkering operation in 2024 as a trial operation, which is likely to involve an inland vessel [40] [41]. Rotterdam is also in a pre-feasibility study considering the set-up of a large green ammonia cracker able to produce 1 MTPA of hydrogen per year, which will require close to 6 MTPA of ammonia. If realised large amount of ammonia will be available in the port area. Also, the port of **Antwerp-Brugges** aims to be able to bunker ammonia in 2024 [42].

Port of **Singapore** is about to embark on one of the first commercial project in the world to utilize ammonia for bunkering with a capacity of at least 100 kTPA, in addition to using it to generate electricity by a gas turbine [43]. The Port Authority of Singapore expects ammonia bunkering to take place in its water from 2026, following the delivery of its first ammonia-fuelled vessels [44].

The national logistics company of Oman Asyad Group recommends that **Oman** positions itself as the ideal midway bunker hub between Singapore and Rotterdam [45]. New bunkering pattern is expected to develop when ammonia volumes increase, and Oman is well positioned for the container trade passing through there area. There are several options available, and one is that there will be a differentiation between the three deepwater ports in Oman and that Duqm will be focusing on ammonia from Oman and possibly UAE [46].

There are several initiatives for ammonia bunkering in Europe outside the ARA region. In **Norway** Yara has pre-ordered 15 floating bunkering terminals from Azane Fuel Solutions to establish a fuel bunker network in Scandinavia [47] [48]. The barges will also have the options of truck loading and unloading. The goal in 2022 was to establish the bunkering network by 2024. The Norwegian port of Florø claims that it will get the first filling stations for ships with a barge with capacity of 1 000 m³ ammonia [49].

At the same time plans were presented for a bunker hub in Bornholm in **Denmark** by the Baltic Sea. The bunkering should include ammonia in 2025 [50].

In **Germany** Hapag-Lloyd, Mabanaft and AirProducts are working on a large-scale green ammonia import terminal in Hamburg and are also evaluating the options of ship bunkering [51]. Mabanaft is

also a shareholder in ammonia production facility Gulf Coast Ammonia and is exploring opportunities for development of bunkering infrastructure along the **US** Gulf Coast.

In USA, a water borne ammonia terminal owned by Vopak Moda Houston was commissioned in December 2021 and is fully operational and ready for a range of purposes including bunkering [52].

In the Pilbara ports in **Western Australia**, the World's largest bulk exports take place with 752 MTPA of trade with more than 6 800 vessel visits [53]. Western Australia extracts one third of the global iron ore production, mainly in the Pilbara region [54]. At the same time, Western Australia has announced a number of ammonia production projects, including at the Yara facility in Pilbara [3]. The combination caters for the option of using ammonia as a fuel for ore-carrying ships. Yara Clean Ammonia have signed a collaboration agreement with Pilbara Ports Authority to facilitate the uptake of ammonia as a marine fuel in the area [55]. A study carried out by West Australia – East Asia Iron Ore Green Corridor Consortium has found that ships along this route may be fuelled by clean ammonia as early as 2028 [56] and a 5% uptake in 2030. The ammonia usage will be ramped up in mid 2030s. In the scenario, there will be 23 ammonia-powered ships in 2030, 81 in 2035 and 360 in 2050 [57]. Key limiting factors to realize this scenario are availability of suitable engines and regulations in place.

Figure 6: Envisioned ammonia fuel use for transporting iron ore from Pilbara to East Asia from Ref [57]

Ammonia terminals. Ammonia is a traded commodity and there are existing terminals for this in many ports. These terminals may be used as bases for filling bunkering ships that can be operated in the surrounding region. Hence, when bunkering ships and related standards are in place, the terminals are good starting points for bunkering ammonia. Currently grey/brown ammonia is transported, but these terminals can also be used for green and blue ammonia. Existing terminals can be found on the DNV's Alternative Fuel Insight platform and they are shown for Asia in Figure 7.

Gas carriers that are transporting ammonia between the terminals are technically the most convenient ship type to be fuelled by ammonia since they have ammonia available in both ends and the crew is used to the safety precautions of ammonia as a cargo already [1]. However, the IGC code is preventing toxic cargo, including ammonia, to be used as a fuel.

Figure 7: Existing ammonia terminals. Source: Alternative Fuel Insight, DNV [16].

4 Green corridors

Green corridors may be established along main shipping routes and can alleviate the barriers of introducing entirely new value chains for zero-emission fuels like ammonia. They can improve the technical, economic and regulatory feasibility [58]. Green corridors can be an efficient approach in the scaling up from demonstrations and pilots to a platform where a zero-emission fuel becomes significant. It can be the best approach to the gradual transformation of the fuel logistics. Green corridors will reduce the risks of the first movers.

In order for green corridors to be successful, several stakeholders need to collaborate, cf. Figure 8 and further detailed in Figure 9. The alternative fuel like ammonia needs to be produced and delivered with available bunkering infrastructure. There must be a demand for ammonia for ship operators (or cargo owners), which might need policy incentives or regulation to narrow the cost gap to traditional oil-based fuel. In addition, there must be regulation in place for use of ammonia in a safe manner.

Figure 8: Stakeholder that may be involved in a green corridor. From Ref. [59].

Figure 9: Set of core actors involved in a green corridor based on iron ore transport. From Ref. [58].

The barriers for starting a transition to alternative fuel are easier to overcome on fixed trading routes than on tramp shipping.

In a report from by among others Global Maritime Forum possible green corridors were evaluated and compared [58]. Based on the possible emission reductions and how easy they are to implement Figure 10 was prepared. A more detailed analysis of the selected green corridors is presented in Table 1.

Based on possible emission reductions, four green corridors are good candidates with current fuel emissions of more than 10 MTPA: Transport from Australia to China of iron ore, from Brazil to China of iron ore, transpacific containers and from Asia to Europe of containers. Of these four the transport of iron ore from Brazil to China is a long distance and might require intermediate bunkering stations and transpacific has limited feasibility in terms of stakeholders and nations involved.

Figure 10: Evaluation of identified green corridors in terms of feasibility and impact (possible emission reductions) from Ref. [58]

Table 1: Analysis of 10 green corridors against impact (first two rows) and feasibility (last three rows) from Ref. [58].

	Australia-China Iron ore	Brazil- China Iron ore	Australia-Japan Iron ore	Transpacific Containers	Asia-Europe Containers	Transatlantic Containers	North-South Containers	Saudi-India Ammonia	Asia-US Automotive	Saudi-China Methnaol
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
kgCO ₂ e/t _{cargo}	28	48	29	61	93	56	99	104	197	137
MtCO ₂ e	20.2	10.5	1.9	12.3	21.7	3.2	1.5	0.3	0.9	0.16
Fuel cost increased of traded good (%)	11%	28%	11%	3%	2%	2%	12%	4%	1%	4%
National policies/regulation 1=low; 5=high	2	2	4	1	3	3	4	1	3	1
Ease of stakeholder environment 1=low; 5= high	2	5	4	1	1	1	2	4	5	4

The container route between Asia and Europe has high emission reduction potential and the cost of traded goods would only increase by 2%. Bunkering in the Middle East would improve the feasibility.

For transport of iron ore from Western Australia, the national policies/regulations and stakeholder environment for starting the transport was considered favored in Japan compared to China – even though the emissions are an order of magnitude less [58]. Also, the feasibility of automotive transport, in particular for electric vehicles, between Asia and US was considered high, even though the emission reductions are limited. Hence the reference concluded with three most feasible green corridors numbered 3, 5 and 9 in Table 1 [58].

Effect of policies and regulations on green corridors. There are several ways that policies and regulation may encourage green corridors. In foreseeable future oil-based marine fuels will remain cheaper than clean ammonia. Gray or brown varieties of ammonia does not reduce the GHG footprint and might compete with food production if the existing producing is going to be used.

However, in 2023 the IMO GHG strategy was strengthened, among others, from a total GHG emission reduction from maritime sector from 50% in 2050 to 70-80% in 2040. For this to happen, significant progress is required, which has to involve alternative fuels. Regulations and/or policies will need to come in place. IMO DCS (and similarly EU MRV) was introduced with a view to inform further IMO measures to reduce GHG emissions from ships [60]. Related to this, EEXI and CII were introduced as short term measures to reduce, and similar regulation may develop [60].

Another important part of regulation is to develop safety rules and regulation for ammonia-fuelled ships. Several class societies have developed classification rules. Ammonia is currently not covered by specific regulations in the IGF Code, and hence approval is based on a risk-based approval process referred to as the alternative design approach. Subject to Flag Administration acceptance, classification rules can be applied partly or fully to comply with Flag Administration requirements. In addition, IMO CCC are working on preparing interim guidelines for ammonia-fuelled ships with target completion at the CCC10 meeting in September 2024. When IMO safety regulations are established,

this may facilitate faster uptake of ammonia as a fuel. There are several parallel activities in CCC for various alternative fuels. Development of safety standards for bunkering of ammonia is also important.

An examples of policies that will influence alternative fuel uptake is the Fuel-EU Maritime regulation in Europe that will reduce the cost difference to alternative fuels significantly. A global CO₂ tax scheme for maritime fuels would have a similar effect on alternative fuels uptake. Also, public support of part of the capital expenditure or credit guarantees would have a positive effect.

Also establishing LCA requirements on EU and global level for alternative fuels on both well-to-tank basis and tank-to-wake basis are very important, for reducing the risks for investment in the multitude of production pathways to the alternative fuels.

4.1 Green corridor from Western Australia to East Asia (iron ore)

The trade of iron ore from Australia to East Asia is about 7% of global trade volumes in tonnes for a route [58]. In Australia iron mining is dominated by three companies Rio Tinto, BHP and Fortescue Metal Group, that are all committed to net-zero targets. Furthermore, there are many initiatives on green and blue ammonia [3], where 54 MTPA of production capacity was announced by mid 2023. Not of all that capacity will be realized, but there could be sufficient ammonia available for iron ore export. According to Table 1, 22.1 MtCO₂e may be removed, which corresponds to about 7 MTPA of VLSFO or 15.7 MTPA ammonia. Part of this ammonia supply may be used to bunker the ships in Singapore on their way back to the Pilbara region in Western Australia, cf. Figure 11, in case the range of the bulkers is not sufficient or if bunkering becomes available in Singapore first. However, deviations from the trade route may become costly [57].

It may be considered a benefit that with few companies are involved in cooperating on green transport that can reduce their emissions on both ends of the trade. Unlike today's trade, it would require dedicated ammonia-powered ships to serve the green corridor.

Figure 11: Green corridors for transporting iron ore from Western Australia to East Asia may have two workable bunkering options. From Ref. [57].

There are only three ports (Port Dampier, Port Hedland and Port Walcott) that export iron ore and hence the bunkering facilities can be built in a concentrated area. This would be cost efficient. Bunkering can e.g. be started in one of the ports and gradually expanded until all ships can be bunkered with ammonia. 6 800 vessel visits per year [53] would require about 19 completed bunkering operations per day on average.

For this green corridor, ammonia appear to be a better choice given the scarcity of biogenic CO₂ in Australia needed to produce methanol, which might become a major competing shipping fuel for other shipping segments.

4.2 Green corridor: The Asia-Europe container route

The container route between East Asia and Europe according to Table 1 has a similar GHG emission reduction potential as the iron ore export from Australia to East Asia, i.e. about 20 MTPA of CO₂, which would require about 15 MTPA ammonia.

Figure 12: Example of a container trade from East Asia to Europe. From Ref. [58]

For this green corridor, there are several benefits compared to the iron ore green corridor mentioned above. The cost increase of the traded goods is only 2%. There will also be EU regulation, like FuelEU Maritime, that will reduce the cost gap further. For the transportation, there are few entities involved with the same cargo owner in both ends, not a buyer and a seller. Furthermore, the cargo transported are closer to final customer, and the cargo owner may be able to share some of their marginal transportation cost with the customer and possibly differentiate their offering from competitors. Hence a low GHG emission transport can be demanded from the cargo owners to the ship operator.

70% of the TEU capacity for this corridor is served by five shipping lines, that are committed to GHG reductions.

In terms of availability of ammonia for bunkering, Singapore is by far the largest bunkering hub today and they are considering ammonia as a fuel, which might be purchased from Australia or the Middle East. There is significant announced clean ammonia capacity in the Middle East by Egypt, Saudi Arabia, Oman and UAE, which would likely make bunkering available in that region. Furthermore, there are announced capacity in Morocco by Gibraltar and Rotterdam intend to import large amounts of ammonia. Hence, there should be sufficient bunkering possibilities along the route even with a reduced range for the ships.

There are many different cargo owners for the container trade. However, some large cargo owners like Amazon and Ikea have established a consortium called Zero Emission Maritime Buyers Alliance (ZEMBA) to provide zero-emission transport at an elevated cost [19].

According to the Global Maritime Forum report [58], a small-scale bunkering facility would increase the fuel cost by 5%, but with a 100% of the fleet on ammonia would give one order of magnitude less bunkering cost. For this trade, also methanol has been suggested as an alternative fuel.

4.3 Green corridor: East Asia – US car carriers

Figure 13: Green corridor for transportation of cars from South-Korea and Japan to Western US. From Ref. [58].

The third green corridor identified by the Global Maritime Forum report [58] is transport of cars between Japan and South Korea to west coast of USA. In the future, this could also involve cars from China. The traded goods are valuable and hence the cost additions for using ammonia as a fuel is only 1%. About 60 RoRo ships are involved in the trade and they are relatively dedicated to the trade. Hence there are possibilities to make a green corridor even though the total emission reductions will be limited to about 0.9 MtCO_{2e}.

In particular for electric vehicles, zero-emission transport is a natural extension. Japanese car manufacturers have shown interest in reducing their GHG footprint. Also shipping companies with RoRo vessel have shown interest in ammonia [31] [61]. For this trade 5 operators are covering 70% of the trade [58].

However, some issues also need to be taken into account. Ammonia might be needed to be transported a significant distance to both ends of the trade. Furthermore, with a relatively long sailing distance and expensive cargo, the value of lost cargo volume may become relevant.

5 Bunkering transition to ammonia

Eventually, if ammonia becomes an important fuel and takes about a third of the marine fuel market, ammonia will be available in most regions. However, it cannot start suddenly everywhere at once, and it must be gradually introduced.

In order for ships to use ammonia, the fuel has to be available in the right places, where the ammonia-powered ships are and with a cargo-owner willing to take the additional cost or with sufficient stringent regulations. There are a couple of such cases. One such example is for ammonia carriers where ammonia is available in both ends and where the crew already are experienced with the safety issues for ammonia. An ammonia VLGC carrier typically (e.g. for the trade from Qatar to China) consumes fuel in the main engine corresponding to 2.6% of the energy of the ammonia it is transporting.

Another special case is the ship Yara Eyde, where Yara will produce the fuel (green ammonia) at the same place they are producing fertilizer, that needs to be exported. This is a nice combination of green transportation and being a forerunner for ammonia as a marine fuel. Yara Eyde is planned to be operated between Norway and Northern Germany.

Ammonia is in general most favorable on long-distance shipping where there are few alternatives that are without GHG emissions available and where it is not needed with frequent bunkering close to populated area, like ferries do. In many cases, green corridor is considered crucial in most cases for introduction ammonia as a fuel to long distance shipping. A consequence of this is that in some shipping segments, ammonia will not be widely used in the beginning. One such segment could be tankers (except ammonia carriers) that are not operating in such an established trade pattern.

Other segments where ammonia not necessarily will be used are the cruise and ropax segments, due to toxicity and smell. Safety experience from cargo carrier should be gained first.

In the further work we decided to further analyze the two green corridors that were considered most promising: Iron ore transport from Australia to East Asia and container transport from Asia to Europe.

5.1 Iron-ore transportation from Australia to East Asia

5.1.1 Current trade of iron-ore from Australia

The current trade of iron-ore with dry bulk ships from Australia to the East-Asian territories China, Taiwan, South-Korea and Japan was analyzed by AIS data, and the fuel consumption was investigated by the Master 2.0 model [62] that also makes use of technical ship data from the IHS database.

The iron-ore are exported from three ports in Pilbara that are close to each other: Port Hedland, Dampier and Port Walcott. About 94% of the transport capacity for dry bulk ship voyages were destined directly to the four territories mentioned above and further analysis was focused on this.

The number of voyages from Pilbara are large with 4 000 to 5 000 each year from 2020 to 2023, cf. Figure 14. Port Hedland is the largest of the three ports, with about twice as many port visits as Dampier and Port Walcott. The ports are situated on a part of the shore of Western Australia of about 200 km.

In order to give an estimate of the **transport capacity** for these ships filling cargo in the Pilbara ports, deadweight tonnes (DWT) were used. In addition to cargo, DWT also includes fuel, fresh water, ballast water, crew and provisions. Hence the use of DWT will necessarily to a certain degree be an overestimate for the cargo. Also, the ships do not have to be completely filled for all voyages. Nevertheless, DWT is considered a fairly representative value for the purpose of this study.

Figure 14: Number of port visits for dry bulk carriers in each of the three Pilbara ports (and the total of them) from 2020 to 2023 based on AIS data.

Monthly values of transport capacity are shown in Figure 15. Further details on annual basis are given in Table 2, which describes the number of yearly ship visit, the number of unique ships (i.e. the number of different IMO numbers of dry bulk carriers) and the total transport capacity. There are about 2 to 4 ship visits on average for each ship within a year, and this ratio appears to be higher in Port Hedland than the other ports.

Figure 15: Transport capacity of iron ore from Pilbara for the dry bulk carrier voyages for each month from 2020 to 2023, as estimated from the sum of DWT over all voyages based on AIS data.

Table 2: Annual numbers for the three ports in Pilbara (and the total thereof) for number of ship visit, number of unique ships and total transport capacity.

	2020	2021	2022	2023
#Ship visits				
Port Walcott	1 025	950	758	1 037
Port Hedland	2 937	2 888	2 491	3 158
Dampier	873	809	678	887
Total	4 835	4 647	3 927	5 082
#Unique ships				
Port Walcott	466	482	412	458
Port Hedland	965	977	931	1 105
Dampier	508	506	443	480
Total	1 335	1365	1284	1 306
Transport capacity (tonnes/year)				
Port Walcott	198 783 450	184 434 046	147 797 079	199 365 099
Port Hedland	561 853 226	548 426 232	465 358 786	601 047 231
Dampier	147 341 253	135 769 773	111 751 821	152 966 540
Total	907 977 929	868 630 051	724 907 686	953 378 870

Official numbers from the Government of Western Australia indicates sales of 844 Mt of iron ore from Western Australia in 2021/2022 (likely referring to July 2021 to June 2022), out of which 98% is mined in Pilbara [54]. This corresponds to 827 Mt from Pilbara. 87% of the iron ore amounts was mined by the three companies mentioned above [54]. In terms of value the export to China is 82%, Japan 7.7%, South Korea 6.1%, Taiwan 2.1% with the remaining at 2.1% in total [54]. The estimated transport capacity from AIS data in Table 2 is relatively close to this official value.

In 2023, our approach indicates an export of 776 Mt (81%) to China, 67.8 Mt (7.1%) to Japan, 55.2 Mt to South Korea (5.8%) and 21.4 Mt (2.2%) to Taiwan, i.e. in total 96.6% of the transport capacity of the dry bulk ships leaving Pilbara, cf. Table 3.

Table 3: Export of iron ore from Pilbara as estimated by summing the DWT of the ships sailing directly to the four territories. Based on AIS data.

Export to:	2020	2021	2022	2023
China	700 745 104	661 089 449	487 781 989	776 187 501
South Korea	60 958 453	68 893 286	73 201 375	55 192 703
Taiwan	22 033 371	22 617 097	23 818 067	21 407 051
Japan	62 912 703	74 042 054	71 696 050	67 837 754

As visible in Figure 15, the export of iron ore from Pilbara decreased from the end of 2021 to the end of 2022, and this was related to China and not to any significant effect the other three territories. This decrease correlates with the decrease in iron ore prices from 200 to 100 USD/tonne in end of 2021, and has been explained by enforced steel production cuts in China to reduce emissions and to a downturn in the property and construction sectors [54]. Chinese policies changed through the first half of 2022 and the iron ore prices partly recovered [54].

The market conditions for iron ore from Australia are also reflected in the average speed of ships between Australia and China, which for the years 2020 to 2023 were 10.86, 10.81, 9.04 and 10.49 knots, respectively. Ship speeds were hence lower, when the iron ore prices were lower. Oil prices were also elevated in 2022.

The typical size of the ships carrying iron ore, that visited Pilbara are also available in the data. Most ships are in a narrow range from 170 to 210 kDWT, cf. Figure 16. Hence a typical bulk ship in this region can be said to be 200 kDWT.

The bunkering capacity of fuel oil are available in the IHS database for many of the ships and since it linearly scales with DWT, by doing a linear regression analysis of the data provided, we modelled Bunker capacity (in m³) = 190 + 0.0287 * DWT. Hence, with a 200 kDWT ship, the bunkering capacity is about 6 000 m³.

Figure 16: The size distribution of the ships visiting the three Pilbara port from 2020 to 2023. In addition, there were about 1500 ship visit with ships smaller than 150k as well as about 1500 ships larger than 250k. Derived from AIS and IHS data.

The **average fuel consumption** for ship larger than 170 kDWT of all the one-way voyages to China, South Korea, Taiwan and Japan in the years 2020 to 2023 were determined to 509, 557, 397 and 560 tonnes of fuel oil for the main engines, respectively. The distribution of fuel consumption is shown in Figure 17. The distribution of the fuel consumption makes it possible to determine the “*high*” fuel consumption, by which most ships (roughly 80%) would be able to go from Australia to the respective countries. This fuel consumptions are 700, 700, 480 and 650 tonnes, respectively.

It is worth mentioning that on average, the existing oil-fuelled large bulk carriers can go from Australia to Japan and back about five times on a fully bunkered ship before needing to bunker again.

Table 4: Current VLSFO fuel consumption for iron ore transportation to East Asia (one-way).

	FC oil (average)/t	FC oil (high)/t
China	509	700
South Korea	557	700
Taiwan	397	480
Japan	560	650

Figure 17: Distribution of fuel consumption (oil) from Pilbara, Australia to China, Japan, South Korea and Taiwan in the years 2020 to 2023. Fuel consumption modelled from AIS and IHS data.

Time required for a return trip. It is valuable to determine the time for a return trip (two transit times and two port stay times) in order to be able to estimate the required amounts of dedicated ships need to serve the current trade of iron ore. Based on AIS data from all voyages from 2020 to 2023, it takes on average for a one-way trip to China, South Korea, Taiwan and Japan 344, 346, 258 and 372 hours.

Figure 18: Distribution of time in ports of Pilbara for the time period 2020 to 2023. Based on AIS data.

The distribution for the **duration of the port stays** in Pilbara are shown in Figure 18, based on all AIS data in the period. The average is 41 hours, and the majority of the ships stay shorter than 48 hours. If the unloading times are equally long and if the return trip to Australia are at the same speed, a return trip can in theory take between about 26 days (Taiwan) and 35 days (Japan).

The estimated number of return trips in a year should also take into account inefficiencies in the logistics chain and maintenance of ships. By assuming an 85% availability of the ships, each ship can have 8 to 12 return trips each year and thereby transport between 1.6 and 2.4 Mt of iron ore each out of Australia, depending on the destination.

5.1.2 Replacement of current iron trade with fully ammonia-fuelled vessels

It is possible to estimate the implications of a transition from oil-fuelled to ammonia-fuelled vessel on the iron-ore trade from Australia to China, South Korea, Taiwan and Japan by assuming the same trade patterns and volumes as described in Chapter 5.1.1. Then the trade volumes will stay at the same level as in 2020-2023, which is about 850 Mt/year.

We have assumed the same transportation times both ways as determined from voyages from Australia today. Furthermore, that the port stays for unloading is of similar duration as for loading today, i.e. 48 hours, and that the cargo is unloaded in one port only. This means a 26 to 35 days return trip, and therefore 8 to 12 return trips per year.

In terms of fuel consumption for the return trips, it has for simplicity been assumed to be twice of the fuel consumption mentioned in Table 4, on energy basis. By taking into account the energy contents for oil-based fuel and ammonia as well as the density of ammonia, the required *average* and *high* (80% of operations) volumes of ammonia for a return trip has been estimated as shown in Table 5. Taking the high values of the fuel consumption, which would be sufficient for most return trips, the consumption in volumes is modelled to be up to about 4 500 m³ ammonia. Hence a 4 500 m³ tank capacity (inner volume as opposed to total tank volume which is larger [63]) would cover one return trip and it is likely, at least in the beginning, that bunkering would be done for every return trip because of the costs and space limitations for deck tanks. This is different from the situation today for fuel oil where a couple of voyages may be done.

It should be noted that 8 of the bulk ships already on order for 2025/2026 in China are planned to be equipped with 3 000 m³ tank capacity (see above), which on average will be close to cover the return trip for an average trip to China. Because of the cargo operations that may damage the tanks, tanks should be placed in the back of the ship, either behind or next to the superstructure.

However, if the ships can be bunkered with ammonia in East Asia as well, the necessary tank capacity would be cut in half. Large two-stroke engines used in iron-ore carriers would likely be dual fuel and hence in case of bad weather, they could as an emergency run on oil-based fuels. One example of this is the Berge Bulk ship, planned to be powered by ammonia [29].

Table 5: Average and high estimates for ammonia consumption for a return trip from Australia for the same ship and operations as for Table 4.

	FC NH ₃ (average)/m ³	FC NH ₃ (high)/m ³
China	3 299	4 538
South Korea	3 611	4 538
Taiwan	2 573	3 112
Japan	3 630	4 214

The average annual fuel consumption for each of the four territories are shown in Table 6, together with the corresponding fuel consumption if all ships were to be fuelled by ammonia. The current fuel oil consumption is about 4.4 MTPA, which corresponds to 9.7 MTPA ammonia. This is a substantial part of the announced clean ammonia production, even for Australia.

Furthermore, the transport work for each territory is shown, and based on the transport time for an average return trip to these territories, the minimum number of ships necessary are shown in Table 6. In total about 455 ships would be able to serve the green corridor given an efficient logistics.

For comparison, about 1 300 different ships called Pilbara port each of the last years, cf. Table 2, but a detailed study of which potential other trades these ships were involved in was not carried out.

Table 6: Total fuel consumption (both ways) for export of iron ore from Australia to the respective countries, averaged over the years 2020-2023. Corresponding estimates for transport amount of iron ore is also presented. The estimated number of ships to serve each country are given in the right column.

	Fuel oil consumption per year (ktonnes)	Ammonia consumption per year / (ktonnes)	Transport work Σ DWT (ktonnes/year)	#Ships
China	3 527	7 724	656 461	365
South Korea	363	799	64 461	36
Taiwan	98	217	22 469	10
Japan	422	929	69 122	44
Sum	4 409	9 719	812 604	455

It has been suggested that Singapore could be used for bunkering on the back to Pilbara, cf. Figure 11. However, based on AIS data only very few of the bulk ships involved in the trade were found to go via Singapore to Australia. Also, the distance travelled would be significantly longer; from Taiwan it would be about 20% longer to go via Singapore to Pilbara, where from Japan it would be about 25% longer. Hence, the tank capacity should either be sufficient to go on a return trip from Pilbara or an ammonia bunkering infrastructure is required in the country receiving the iron ore.

5.1.3 Transition to the green corridor operated on ammonia

Transition from today's oil-based ship to ammonia-fuelled ships cannot happen instantaneously, but rather has to be a gradual change. This may e.g. go through an emergence phase (where coordinated testing takes place), a diffusion stage (coordinated policies to improve economies of scale) where the largest increase takes place, followed by a reconfiguration phase [64]. This approach is based on an S-curve, which has also previously been used to describe the green corridor with iron ore from Australia, cf. Figure 6. In this reference, the S-curve starts in about 2027, has a turning point just before 2040 and flattens out at full decarbonization by 2050.

In this work, the number of ships required in Table 6 is used to prepare the number of ships as a function of time for each corridor in Figure 19 assuming that the introduction of ammonia-fuelled vessels will take the same shape for all territories. However, in reality the willingness to accept ammonia-fuelled vessels in their port and the willingness to pay the additional cost of transportation will likely vary from territory to territory. E.g. Taiwan would only need about 10 dedicated vessels in order to deliver the iron ore in an GHG-free way from Australia, which may be done more quickly than to build/retrofit 36 times more ships for China. The curves in Figure 19 is based on the assumption of a turning point mid-way between 2027 and 2050, and that the bunkering starts with 2% of the ships in 2027, i.e. about 10 ships, which is about the total number of bulk ships on order as of June 2024.

Figure 19: Modelled number of ships required for the Australian iron-ore green corridor to each of the countries.

As mentioned above, about 9.7 MTPA clean ammonia would be necessary to fuel all iron-ore bulk carrier from Australia at today's export rate and trade pattern. A similar S-curve may therefore be made for the fuel consumption and given that the ships in general are quite similar, this will be an acceptable approach, cf. Figure 20. This indicates a need for 1 MTPA in 2030 and 6.2 MTPA in 2040.

Figure 20: Modelled ammonia fuel consumption as a function of time for an S-shaped transition to ammonia for an iron-ore green corridor from Australia to East-Asia (Mtonnes/year).

When this is compared to our previous study on ammonia supply and demand [3], then the announced clean ammonia project in Australia up to 2045 is 54.1 MTPA ammonia. Of that 28.1 MTPA are announced to be available in 2030 and 34.1 in 2040. However, not all projects will be realized at all and delays must be expected. Hence, in our balanced scenario, Australia contributes with about 6.4 MTPA in 2030, out of which up to 5.2 MTPA could be available for shipping (if the mixed uses are directed towards shipping). Based on that there will be sufficient clean ammonia from Australia available in 2030, but with more uncertainty towards 2040. In any case a substantial amount of the clean ammonia produced in Australia would be needed to fuel this green iron-ore corridor if this is entirely fuelled from Australia. At the moment, there is a limited amount of announced clean ammonia projects in East Asia, and if bunkering would be done in e.g. China, the probability is high that it will be with Australian ammonia and that this will not change the supply/demand situation. This green corridor has a very good balance between supply of ammonia from the region and a large demand of clean ammonia for export of ore from the same region. This match may be exploited further.

5.2 Analysis of the container trade from Asia to Europe

The container trade from East Asia to Europe was examined with a similar approach as for the iron ore trade from Australia to East Asia. The selection of container ships was based on the criteria that they passed through Malacca strait, Suez Canal and Gibraltar strait in a single journey in 2023 to North-Western Europe (i.e. passed Gibraltar and Spain before subsequently stopping in France, Belgium, Netherlands, UK, Germany, Denmark or Sweden afterwards).

The analysis was focused on voyages originating in China as the last country before passing Singapore. The reason is that ships from South Korea subsequently stop in China and from Japan there were fewer and smaller ships, see below. There were 674 such ship voyages from China with 278 unique ships. The average TEU was 16 064, and ships of that size have about 14 000 m³ bunker oil capacity according to the IHS Fairplay database. 90% of the voyages (610 of the 674) involved a stop in the port of Singapore or Tanjung Pelepas in Malaysia when going westwards. The total duration from China to North-Western Europe for the larger container vessels (above 12 000 TEU) was on average 703 hours (close to 30 days). The sailing distance was on average 9 924 nm and with a total main engine fuel consumption of 3 460 tonnes oil. The average bunker capacity for the container ships allows for about two times back and forth from China (last port) to North-Western Europe (first port). In reality, the container liners visit several ports in Europe and East Asia and hence the total fuel consumption for a round trip is higher.

The distances, duration, average speed and fuel consumption of the larger container vessels were also determined for each segment along the route China - Singapore/Malaysia – Suez - Europe when intermediate stops were detected from AIS data, cf. Table 7.

Table 7: Average distance, duration, speed and fuel consumption for large containership in 2023 (>12 000 TEU) sailing from China to North-Western Europe through the Suez Canal.

Segment	Distance (nm)	Duration (h)	Speed (kt)	Fuel consumption (t)
China-Singapore	1 647	111	15.49	550
Singapore-Suez	4 957	294	17.11	1 723
Suez-Europe	3 309	261	13.30	1 116

For the segment from China to Singapore/Malaysia, the data depends significantly on the starting port. Also, for the next segment to Suez, some ships visit the Persian Gulf on their way, making the segment longer.

It should also be noted that it is about 2 000 nm from Suez to Gibraltar, where the ships in focus are passing. Hence, if bunkering could take place in the Gibraltar region, the last segment could be split in two parts. There is a substantial ammonia production capacity planned in that region [3].

Based on Table 7, it is the segment from Singapore to Suez that is the limiting factor for the tank capacity for an ammonia-fuelled container vessel in the East Asia – Europe trade. Notably, it is also on this segment where the average speed is the highest.

Figure 21: The distribution of fuel consumption for large containerships going from Singapore to Suez in 2023, based on AIS data.

As shown in Figure 21, a bunkering capacity of 2 000 tonnes oil would cover the majority of the voyages from Singapore to Suez. This corresponds to about 4 400 tonnes or 6 500 m³ ammonia. The ammonia consumption would of course depend on the design of the ship and how it is operated, in particular at which speed the ship is sailing. This ammonia amount is about half the oil volume that can be bunkered in these container ships today, but deck tanks of this size will likely reduce the cargo load to some extent.

In theory, it would also be possible to bunker between Singapore and Egypt, in order to reduce the required ammonia tank size. One possible port could be Colombo in Sri Lanka which is close to the shipping route. In that case the longest segment will be about 3 400 nm from Sri Lanka to Egypt, and that distance is similar to the distance from Suez to Rotterdam. Another possibility is Oman, which have announced green ammonia production [3], leading to increased travelled distance because of the detour.

If the container ship additionally stops in Sri Lanka or Oman, the average fuel consumption for the longest segment will be reduced to about 2 500 tonnes or 3 700 m³ ammonia for the main engine. The possible bunkering hubs are shown in Figure 22. The bunkering hubs marked with blue symbols would be possible with larger ammonia tanks, but the green bunkering hubs would make the required tank size smaller as also shown by the symbol size. A further tank size reduction would be achieved by bunkering in the locations marked by red.

Figure 22: Illustration of a container ship route from East Asia to North-Western Europe with required bunkering hubs shown in blue, whereas additional bunkering hubs in green and red would reduce the required tank size further, as highlighted by the size of the symbols.

If the ships are equipped with sufficiently large ammonia tanks to reach Egypt from Singapore, then the ships may be bunkered in Singapore both in eastbound and westbound directions. In that case more than 8 000 nm of the about 20 000 nm round trip may be covered with bunker from Singapore. However, this is of course a simplified approach since container ships typically stop in several ports in East Asia, and bunkering in China and South Korea would likely be required for full ammonia operations.

From the container vessel visiting Japan in 2023, 42 voyages reached Singapore/Malaysia directly, without stopping in China. These ships are smaller with an average TEU of 8 613, and were analysed separately. The average speed was 16.8 kt, the duration 176 hours and with a distance of 2 935 nm. The fuel consumption was 782 tonnes of oil. This corresponds to about 2 500 m³ ammonia. These smaller ships consume less fuel, and the average consumption is 1 334 tonnes from Singapore to Suez, which is 23% less than the average ship from China. The fuel consumption of this longest Japan-Europe segment corresponds to about 4 350 m³ ammonia, on average.

The **total fuel consumption** for all the 674 ship voyages between China (last port) and North-Western Europe (first port) is about 2.3 MTPA oil. The fuel consumption for the return trip would be 4.6 MTPA and if including all stops in East Asia and Europe, the fuel consumption is significantly higher. This corresponds to more than 10 MTPA ammonia for this scope of container ship voyages between Asia and North-Western Europe.

6 Concluding remarks

Based on the results above, ammonia bunkering will first be introduced in special cases and well-suited green corridors, before the market possibly matures at a significant size. One such case is ammonia carriers where clean ammonia is available and where less training on safety issues is required; seven such ships are on order. Another case is the ship delivering fertilizer from a green ammonia plant in Norway to fixed ports in Germany. Other ships on fixed routes are also possibly, and two crude oil tanker have been ordered with an ammonia engine as well.

Considering the likely supply of green ammonia in Australia and the limited number of parties involved, a promising green corridor is the transport of iron ore from three Pilbara ports in Australia to East Asia. A large amount of about 800 Mt iron ore is exported each year with at least 4 000 ship voyages. It should be possible to operate bulk ships on ammonia on this corridor and the calculated tank size is about 4 500 m³. Then the vast majority of these voyages would be fully on ammonia with bunkering only in Pilbara. However, there are several options for reducing the required tank size: a) bunkering in the other end (China, Taiwan, South Korea, Japan), and b) by considering the *average* fuel consumption needed instead of the clear *majority*. In fact, bulk ships have a large fraction of the ammonia-fuelled ships that currently are on order, with up to 13 of the 25 ships to be ready within 2027. About 455 ships would be required for this green corridor, and if all these bulk ships would be used for iron ore on this trade, then about 3% of the iron ore transport from Australia would be green in 2027. A possible development of the ammonia-fuelled dry-bulk ships in place towards 2050 and their total ammonia fuel consumption are shown with S-curves in this work. Bunkering in Singapore is unlikely for this trade, but bunkering in the import ports in East Asia would make ammonia-fuelled bulk vessels more feasible.

Another possible green corridor is the container trade from East Asia to Europe. It is possible to use ammonia if bunkering of ammonia is available in China/South Korea, Singapore, Egypt and Rotterdam. Tank size should then be about 6 500 m³ to cover the vast majority of the voyages. It would be beneficial for the tank size to have bunkering by Sri Lanka and the tank size could be even more reduced with bunkering both in Oman and Gibraltar, cf. map in Figure 22. Operations to Japan does not increase the tank size as long as the ships can be bunkered in Japan.

The overall ammonia consumption will be significant for these two green corridors with close to 10 MTPA for the iron-ore corridor and more than 10 MTPA for the container trade. For these two trades, the announced clean ammonia projects in Australia could cover the ammonia demand in Australia, East Asia and Singapore. Further west on the container trade, ammonia fuel demand could be sufficiently covered from the announced projects in the Middle East and by Gibraltar.

7 References

- [1] H. W. Brinks and E. Hektor, "Ammonia as a marine fuel," DNV White Paper, 2020.
- [2] H. W. Brinks, O. Ivashenko, T. Wang, B. E. Bakken and H. A. Tvetve, "Foresight report on future availability of green/blue ammonia in 2030, 2040 and 2050," <https://zenodo.org/records/10043691>, 2023.
- [3] H. W. Brinks, O. Ivashenko, B. E. Bakken, T. Wang and H. A. Tvetve, "Availability of green and blue ammonia in 2030 to 2050," DNV White Paper, 2024.
- [4] M. Campbell and e. al, "Study of the readiness and availability of low- and zero carbon ship technology and marine fuels," IMO, Ricardo, DNV, 2023.
- [5] "Ship Technology," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ship-technology.com/projects/portofsingapore/>.
- [6] N. Lim and R. N. S. Sahu, "Feature: Singapore weak barging spreads dampen time charter market for bunker tankers," S&P Global Commodity Insights, 2 July 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.spglobal.com/commodityinsights/en/market-insights/latest-news/shipping/070221-feature-singapore-weak-barging-spreads-dampen-time-charter-market-for-bunker-tankers>.
- [7] "Maritime and Port Authority of Singapore," 2023. [Online]. Available: [https://www.mpa.gov.sg/port-marine-ops/marine-services/bunkering/lng-bunkering-\(pilot-programme\)](https://www.mpa.gov.sg/port-marine-ops/marine-services/bunkering/lng-bunkering-(pilot-programme)).
- [8] Port of Rotterdam, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.portofrotterdam.com/en/experience-online/facts-and-figures>.
- [9] Port of Rotterdam, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.portofrotterdam.com/en/sea-shipping/bunkering-in-rotterdam>.
- [10] GCaptain, 4 March 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://gcaptain.com/man-energy-solutions-to-offer-ammonia-fueled-ship-engines-after-2027/>.
- [11] Offshore Energy, 15 November 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.offshore-energy.biz/wartsila-rolls-out-industrys-first-4-stroke-ammonia-engine/>.
- [12] WinGD, [Online]. Available: <https://www.wingd.com/en/engines/engine-types/methanol-and-ammonia/>. [Accessed 18 March 2024].
- [13] WinGD, 21 December 2023. [Online]. Available: https://www.wingd.com/en/documents/technical-information-notes/wingd_tino35_dual-fuel-ammonia-engine-development/.
- [14] Maritime Port Authority of Singapore, 15 March 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mpa.gov.sg/media-centre/details/world-s-first-use-of-ammonia-as-a-marine-fuel-in-a-dual-fuelled-ammonia-powered-vessel-in-the-port-of-singapore>.
- [15] Chemistry World, 18 December 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.chemistryworld.com/news/pioneering-ammonia-powered-ship-shows-off-a-greener-future-for-shipping-at-cop28/4018648.article#:~:text=Fortescue%E2%80%99s%20ship%20the%20Green%20Pioneer%20ois%20designed%20as,in%20Singapore%2C%20however%2C%20because%2>.
- [16] "Alternative Fuel Insight platform," DNV, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://afi.dnv.com/>.
- [17] Marine Log, 9 Aug 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.marinelog.com/news/japans-first-lng-fueled-tug-to-be-converted-for-ammonia-fuel/#:~:text=Japan%27s%20first%20LNG-fueled%20tug%2C%20the%20Sakigake%2C%20is%20to,to%20modify%20a%20tugboat%20to%20ammonia%20fuel%20specifications..>
- [18] Eidesvik, [Online]. Available: <https://eidesvik.no/innovation/eidesvik-and-ship-fc-piloting-ammonia-fuel-cell-for-zero-emission/>.
- [19] Offshore Energy, 10 March 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.offshore-energy.biz/zero-emission-maritime-buyers-alliance-launched-to-boost-net-zero-drive/>.

- [20] Offshore Energy, 27 Feb 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.offshore-energy.biz/beihai-shipbuilding-starts-building-cmbs-ammonia-ready-bulker/>.
- [21] “Nihon Shipyard,” 11 April 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.nsync.co.jp/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/240411_news_en.pdf.
- [22] “MarineLog,” 11 April 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.marinelog.com/news/man-bw-ammonia-engine-will-be-piloted-in-new-japanese-bulk-carrier/>.
- [23] Teknisk Ukeblad, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tu.no/artikler/bestiller-forste-containerskip-pa-ammoniakk/544020>.
- [24] Yara, 23 Nov 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.yara.com/corporate-releases/the-worlds-first-clean-ammonia-powered-container-ship/>.
- [25] Teknisk Ukeblad, 12 February 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tu.no/artikler/norsk-teknologi-pa-forste-ammoniakkdrevne-skip/543506>.
- [26] NYK, 25 January 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.nyk.com/english/news/2024/20240125_02.html.
- [27] Splash, 23 May 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://splash247.com/tianjin-southwest-maritime-orders-lpg-ammonia-carriers/>.
- [28] Splash, 24 June 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://splash247.com/tianjin-southwest-maritime-signs-for-more-lpg-ammonia-carriers/>.
- [29] Berge Bulk, 29 February 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bergebulk.com/berge-bulk-orders-two-ammonia-fuelled-newcastlemax-vessels/>.
- [30] AET Tankers, 19 April 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.aet-tankers.com/media-centre/worlds-first-ammonia-dual-fuel-afamax-to-be-developed-by-aet-miscs-petroleum-arm/>.
- [31] Teknisk Ukeblad, 7 March 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tu.no/artikler/hoegh-autoliners-far-146-millioner-i-ammoniakkstotte/544533>.
- [32] Høegh Autoliners, 5 December 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.hoeghautoliners.com/hoegh-autoliners-and-sumitomo-corporation-take-the-helm-in-sustainable-transportation-of-cars>.
- [33] Yara, 2 November 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.yara.com/news-and-media/news/archive/2023/hoegh-autoliners-and-yara-clean-ammonia-partner-to-cut-maritime-emissions/>.
- [34] Høegh Autoliners, 11 May 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.hoeghautoliners.com/news/hoegh-autoliners-accelerates-green-commitment-forms-groundbreaking-ammonia-partnership-with>.
- [35] ENOVA Press release, 19 June 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.enova.no/presse/>.
- [36] Ocean Hyway Cluster, 21 June 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oceanhywaycluster.no/news/amon-maritime-enova-grant>.
- [37] Teknisk Ukeblad, 5 February 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tu.no/artikler/equinor-vil-ha-forsyningsskip-med-ammoniakk-som-drivstoff/543237>.
- [38] Grønt Skipsfartsprogram, 9 September 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://grontskipsfartsprogram.no/pilotprosjekt/bunkring-av-ammoniakk-i-stavangeromradet/>.
- [39] Tradewinds, 2 May 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tradewindsnews.com/bulkers/fortescue-metals-group-aims-to-have-its-vlocs-running-on-ammonia-by-2027/2-1-1443840>.
- [40] “Ship & Bunker,” 16 November 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://shipandbunker.com/news/emea/203098-ibia-convention-rotterdam-expects-first-ammonia-bunkering-in-2024>.
- [41] “Port of Amsterdam,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://shipandbunker.com/news/emea/203098-ibia-convention-rotterdam-expects-first-ammonia-bunkering-in-2024>.
- [42] “Lloyds list,” 29 November 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://lloydslist.com/LL1147443/Port-of->

- Antwerp-Bruges-to-be-alternative-fuel-ready-in-2025.
- [43] “The Straits Times,” 25 October 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.straitstimes.com/singapore/s-pore-a-step-closer-to-using-low-carbon-ammonia-for-bunkering-power-generation>.
- [44] “S&P Global Commodity Insights,” 3 July 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.spglobal.com/commodityinsights/en/market-insights/latest-news/lng/070323-interview-singapores-mpa-sees-first-ammonia-bunkering-from-2026-methanol-pilot-to-pave-way>.
- [45] “The Potential of Hydrogen Transition for Ports in the Sultanate of Oman,” Asyad, https://asyad.om/docs/default-source/hydrogen/asyad_hydrogen-report_2022.pdf, 2022-2023.
- [46] Ammonia Energy Association, 7 March 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ammoniaenergy.org/articles/brooge-energy-and-siemens-energy-to-boost-uae-renewable-ammonia-industry/>.
- [47] Yara International, 1 April 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.yara.com/news-and-media/news/archive/news-2022/yara-international-and-azane-fuel-solutions-to-launch-worlds-first-carbon-free-bunkering-network-delivering-green-ammonia-fuel-to-the-shipping-industry/>.
- [48] “Fleetmon,” 11 April 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fleetmon.com/maritime-news/2022/37881/yara-plans-15-ammonia-bunkering-terminals-scandina/>.
- [49] Skipsrevyen, 7 March 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.skipsrevyen.no/ammoniakk-ammoniakk-fartoy-ammoniakk-floro/vi-har-forberedt-oss-pa-dette-oyeblikket-i-tre-ar/1738535>.
- [50] “Port of Røenne,” 5 April 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://portofroenne.com/press/2022/4/5/international-consortium-aims-to-enable-bunkering-of-sustainable-marine-fuels-on-bornholm-by-2025>.
- [51] The Maritime Executive, 27 January 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://maritime-executive.com/article/hapag-lloyd-explores-ammonia-bunkering-in-germany-and-us-with-mabanaft>.
- [52] Ship and Bunker, 2 November 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://shipandbunker.com/news/world/725841-insight-alt-bunker-fuel-developments-at-key-ports>.
- [53] Yara, 7 November 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.yara.com/news-and-media/news/archive/2023/study-reveals-pilbara-potential-for-ammonia-as-a-clean-shipping-fuel/>.
- [54] “Western Australian Mineral and Petroleum: Statistics digest 2021-2022,” Government of Western Australia, Department of Mines, Industry Regulation and Safety, 2022.
- [55] Pilbara Ports, 28 July 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pilbaraports.com.au/about-ppa/news,-media-and-statistics/news/2022/july/pilbara-region-moves-towards-ammonia-bunkering>.
- [56] Baltic Exchange, 17 May 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://emissions.balticexchange.com/en/news-and-events/news/esg-news/2023/ammonia-fuelled-bulk-carriers-within-five-years.html>.
- [57] “Fuelling the decarbonisation of iron ore shipping between Western Australia and East Asia with clean ammonia,” Global Maritime Forum, 2023.
- [58] M. Parker, R. Chen, J. Christensen, F. Dalsalle and M. Stone, “The Next Wave: Green Corridors,” Global Maritime Forum, 2021.
- [59] DNV, 25 March 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dnv.com/expert-story/maritime-impact/key-considerations-for-establishing-a-green-shipping-corridor/#:~:text=Green%20shipping%20corridors%20can%20fast-track%20the%20adoption%20of,new%20ofuels%20and%20technologies%20on%20a%20manageable%20scale..>
- [60] IMO, [Online]. Available: <https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/Environment/Pages/Improving%20the%20energy%20efficiency%20of%20ships.aspx>. [Accessed 25 March 2024].

- [61] Wallenius Wilhelmsen, 15 August 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.walleniuswilhelmsen.com/news/wallenius-wilhelmsens-next-generation-vessels-are-coming>.
- [62] B. Guo, Q. Liang, H. Tvette, H. Brinks and E. Vanem, "Combined machine learning and physics-based models for estimating fuel consumption of cargo ships," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 255, p. 111435, 2022.
- [63] "Methanol in Shipping," MAN Energy Solutions, Augsburg, Germany.
- [64] T. Smith, D. Baresic, J. Fahnestock, C. Galbraith, C. Perico, I. Rojon and A. Shaw, "A Strategy for the Transition to Zero-Emission Shipping," UMAS & Getting to Zero Coalition, 2021.
- [65] DNV, "Maritime Forecast to 2050 - Energy Transition Outlook 2022," 2022.
- [66] "Low Carbon Shipping Towards 2050," DNV Position Paper, 2017.
- [67] "Energy Transition Outlook 2022 - A global and regional forecast to 2050," DNV, 2022.
- [68] "Western Australian Mineral and Petroleum: Statistics Digest 2021-2022," Government of Australia, Department of mines, Industry Regulations and Safety., 2022.